

Fellows from the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions programme
29. April 2020

Ursula von der Leyen
President of the European Commission
Berlaymont, Rue de la Loi 200
1049 Brussels, Belgium

Subject : Costed extensions for Horizon 2020 fellowships impacted by the covid-19 outbreak

Dear Mrs von der Leyen,

Just 2 weeks ago, you published an inspiring editorial, proudly advocating for European solidarity and announcing a massive financial support program for workers and businesses across the continent. "This solidarity is at the very heart of Europe and that is what will allow it to be reborn," you said. We were all in awe.

Unfortunately, as researchers from the Horizon 2020 programme, we have experienced a different reality. The European Commission has indeed asked many of us to take unpaid leave, in case we were unable to work during the covid-19 outbreak.

We are researchers from the "Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA)" programme - Horizon 2020's flagship individual fellowship programme that are among the most prestigious and competitive in Europe. To promote the exchange of knowledge between and to European countries, the prerequisite for accessing these fellowships is that candidates must move to a European country, other than their own. Obviously, obtaining one of these fellowships relies not only extensive preparation work, but also an extremely ambitious research program, alongside teaching, knowledge transfer and personal development goals. In short, a project that leaves no room to accommodate for periods of inactivity, be it only for a couple of weeks.

Following the covid-19 outbreak, many of us are unfortunately unable to work. There are many reasons for this – closed laboratories, inability to perform field-work, or full-time care responsibilities. As required by the European Commission, all of us are in a country that we do not know, often for only a few months, and therefore without support from our family, friends, and even our hierarchy, which we barely know. Many of us have taken on significant costs to finance a move with our spouses and children, and some of us had to ask our partner to leave his/her work in our home country to make our participation in the MSCA programme possible.

Given these circumstances, many of us asked for our project to be extended, but the response from the European Commission has been daunting : Researchers are welcome to take unpaid leave.

https://ec.europa.eu/research/mariecurieactions/news/coronavirus-extensions-msca-projects_en

The European Commission considers that the costs dedicated to equipment or overheads (which go directly to the university) may be diverted to finance the salaries of researchers during this period. But most universities won't agree to forego on this precious overhead income. As for the equipment costs, these are generally spent at the start of the project, and are rarely available. As another measure, the Commission suggests that researchers should try to access social security benefits in their host countries, but these are very uncertain and many of us simply do not have access to them.

Here again, there are numerous reasons for this and simply disregarding individual situations appears arbitrary. By design of the programme we are part of, most of us won't meet requirements for previous employment history in our host country. While some of us may have social security agreements with our home country, many of us won't. Some of us have come back from engagements outside Europe. Others will have only just finished their PhD (sometimes unpaid or paid through scholarships that exclude social security contributions). For others, social security contributions are insufficient to cover for the expenses they have taken on for the programme. Finally, for many of us with care responsibilities, access to benefits won't be granted in our host country, although research work is thoroughly incompatible with the care of young children. Particularly failing to support caregivers would, as so often, affect women disproportionately.

Many renowned funding agencies are supporting their researchers during this time and have agreed to consider requests for costed extensions. The Wellcome Trust, the German Research Foundation, the Spanish Government, and even some Horizon 2020 projects, are only some of those we are aware of.

We are writing this letter, in the hope that you would please reassess the European Commission's position, under consideration of the special situation faced by MSCA fellows, and perhaps assist fellows with the same level of solidarity that makes the European project so unique and admirable.

Some of us have launched a petition on this matter, and over a thousand of us have already signed:

https://secure.avaaz.org/en/community_petitions/mscareac_representatives_paid_extensions_of_msca_projects_following_disruptions_caused_by_covid19_pandemic

Thank you for your consideration and support.

Kind regards,

A group of research fellows from the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions programme.

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Former MSCA Fellow, Dr. Brian Cahill, MSCA Fellow H2020 Framework Programmes 6 and 7